

SOCIAL COMMERCE: THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCER MARKETING, PERCEIVED VALUE AND TRUST IN DETERMINING THE PURCHASE INTENTION OF FOLLOWERS

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Abstract

Influencer marketing has emerged as a powerful strategy for enhancing brand image, driving sales, and increasing revenue. This study seeks to understand the underlying factors that influence followers' intentions to purchase products recommended by social media influencers (SMIs), particularly in the beauty products within the realm of social commerce. The research specifically examines the effect of influencer marketing, perceived value, and trust on consumers' purchase intentions. Data were collected from a sample of 300 respondents through an online survey and analyzed using SPSS to evaluate the relationships within the proposed conceptual model. The findings reveal that influencer marketing significantly shapes both the perceived value of products and the trust followers place in SMIs, which in turn positively influence purchase intentions. These insights contribute to the growing body of literature on digital consumer behavior and offer practical implications for marketers aiming to optimize their social commerce strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Social commerce is rapidly gaining popularity due to continuous technological development in the digital world (Kassim, Bhattarai, Zamzuri, 2017). As of October 2023, internet users have reached 5.3 billion globally, with nearly 65.7% actively engaging with social media platform (Statista, 2023). Asia alone accounts for 2.9 billion users, making it a crucial region in the global digital economy. This high adoption rate of social media (SM) in human life opens the avenue of social commerce defined as buying and selling of products and services through social media. This growing trend is reshaping how brands interact with consumers, as they are increasingly using social media influencers to connect the target customers.

Influencer Marketing (IM) has emerged as a powerful tool for brands in the context of social commerce.

Social Media Influencers (SMIs) build strong, personal connections with their followers, which plays a substantial role in determining consumer perceptions and purchase intentions. Influencers use their content and various marketing techniques to recommend products and services. Their opinions help build trust among their followers and are perceived as more authentic than traditional advertising. This authenticity makes influencer marketing particularly effective in driving consumer engagement and boosting sales. According to Gomes (2022), consumers tend to trust influencers more than traditional celebrities, viewing them as relatable and reliable sources of product information. As a result, influencer marketing has become a key driver of purchase decisions, especially in industries like

beauty, fashion, and lifestyle, where consumers seek personalized recommendations.

Despite the widespread integration of social commerce by brands, there is limited research that comprehensively explores the factors that drive the purchase intentions among followers of SMIs. Therefore, to develop an understanding of this phenomenon, this study is based on three variables: influencer marketing, perceived value, and trust, which enhances the purchase intention of followers. This study tests these factors in the new model to clearly comprehend the purchase intention of followers in social commerce.

Influencer marketing (IM) plays a substantial role in convincing followers through their marketing activities to increase their purchase intention (PI). IM affects the perceived value of the product which drives trust among consumers. Their marketing efforts help them avoid the uncertainty associated with online transactions (Pons, 2018). Our model includes a new construct of perceived value as it is assumed as an important factor in convincing the followers to purchase products. The existing studies have examined social media marketing, such as the characteristics of influencers on consumer behavior, but very few delve into the combined influence of influencer marketing, perceived value and trust within the setting of social commerce. The research mentioned that influencer marketing (IM) positively impacts the purchase intentions of followers whereas trustworthiness, content value (informational and entertainment) also impact their credibility (Saima, & Khan, M. A, 2020). Thus, very few comprehensively explored crucial factors that influence the purchase intention of followers.

Influencer marketing is evident, however, the mechanism through which it drives consumer purchase intentions (PI), remain unexplored. Specifically, how influencer marketing impacts the perceived value (PV) of a product and builds trust among consumers, which contributes to the decision making process. Moreover, previous research has overlooked how factors in our framework impact the purchase intentions of followers particularly in beauty segments, where influencer marketing plays a crucial role.

Thus, this study fills this gap by developing and testing a novel model empirically that integrates influencer

marketing (IM), perceived value (PV) and trust to predict the purchase intentions of followers within social commerce. By focusing on these constructs, the research not only enriches the existing knowledge but also provides useful insights for brands seeking to optimize their social media strategies. This study sheds light on the influencing mechanism through which influencers build trust among their followers to drive sales in the digital marketplace.

Literature Review and Hypothesis Development:

Theoretical Background:

While research on social commerce, influencer marketing, trust, and purchase intentions is extensive, there are still gaps and limitations that need further investigation. For instance, a study highlights the significant positive relationship between influencer marketing and purchase intentions (Lim et al., 2017). However, other studies have shown that the overly commercial nature of influencer marketing can reduce trust and limit its effectiveness (Martínez-López et al., 2020). Thus, this contradiction suggests that the relationship between influencer marketing and followers is more nuanced than thought and may be context-dependent. Moreover, the role of perceived value has been also explored within the domain of consumer behavior extensively. However, the complex and multidimensional nature of perceived value- both hedonic and utilitarian- remains underexplored in the social commerce perspective (Picot-Coupey, 2021; Morar, 2013; Holbrook, 1982). On the other hand, several studies have treated perceived value as a monolithic construct to see its impact on trust and purchase intentions (Ajina et al., 2019). Thus, this study addresses the limitation by considering perceived value as a mediator between trust and influencer marketing, which is yet to be explored in social commerce.

Studies on social commerce and influencer marketing have used several theories, such as the Technology Acceptance Model, theory of reasoned action, theory of planned behavior, and unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (Zhang, et al., 2016). However, the Unified Theory of Acceptance & Use of Technology 2 (UTAUT2) provides a robust theoretical foundation for understanding technology adoption behavior, which is highly relevant to social commerce. It explains why individuals accept new

technology and use it. It extends the original UTAUT model by adding new factors that influence technology adoption. It states that effort and performance expectancy, social influence, facilities, hedonic motivation, habit, and price value are the seven factors that are believed to affect behavioral intentions (Venkatesh, 2012). UTAUT2 factors are essential for predicting purchase intentions (Venkatesh, Thong, & Xu, 2012). Thus, we build our conceptual model based on this theory by adopting two variables; “price value” and “social influence”. Social influence is the opinions and perceptions of another person that influence the consumer whereas, Price value is the tradeoff between costs and benefits for the consumers. Following this framework, we examine how influencer marketing (IM) and perceived value (PV) affect followers' purchase intentions in social commerce (SC). Additionally, this research explore the role of trust in shaping the purchase intentions.

Influencer Marketing:

Influencers have become a key part of modern marketing strategies. Many brands are using influencers to boost sales, improve brand image, and build stronger connection with customers. Influencer marketing is defined as the “art and science of engaging people who are influential online to share sponsored message with their audiences” (Sammis, 2016). Another definition elaborated on this, describing it as the use of selective persons which hold certain influence over potential buyers of a product or brand through their marketing activities (Evans, Phua, & Jun., 2017).

Social media influencers are often considered digital celebrities, who have established themselves as powerful endorser and are considered as cost effective and efficient source of marketing (Lim et al., 2017). Influencer marketing is rising and become part of strategic planning for the brand, they recommend their products through influencers (Campbell, 2020). Social media influencers hold a significant influence over their follower. They've earned the trust of their followers, allowing their endorsements to influence purchase decisions and motivate specific actions through careful interaction and relationship building tactics. This power has been well-documented by researchers and industry experts (Chi,

Yeh, & Tsai., 2011). While numerous studies highlights the positive impact of influencer characteristics such as expertise and trustworthiness (Gomes et al., 2022; AL-Sous, 2023; Vrontis., 2022), it is important to consider potential context where these factors may not lead to increase purchase intentions. A qualitative study identified relevant key factors of influencer marketing which impacted the consumer behavior. The study identified two factors- attitude toward influencers and perceived behavior control which is increase in domain knowledge as the favorable factors that affect the consumer behavior (Chorpa et al., 2021). Moreover, personal relevance, trust and inspiration had a positive influence on consumer behavior. Consumer follow different influencers for different categories. A study revealed that source attractiveness did not influence consumer purchase intentions (Lim et al., 2017). Although, congruency between product/brand and influencer strongly influence purchase intentions. A study revealed that influencer marketing has a positive effect on consumers (Johansen and Guldvik., 2017).

Influencer marketing is a source that affect the purchase decision of the followers. Fashion and beauty segments are constantly use these influencers to increase purchase of their beauty or cosmetic products. Study conducted on the role of digital influencer on consumer purchase intentions in fashion products reveal that influencer's characteristics play a significant in determining the purchase intentions of the followers. Trustworthiness and expertise are the factors that enhance purchase intentions of the followers (Gomes et al., 2022). Another study revealed that Instagram influencers affect the purchase intentions of young females particularly source credibility with subdimensions of trustworthiness, expertise, attractiveness is positively linked with the consumer purchase intentions. The study was based on empirical findings conducted on 306 German Instagram users of young age (Weismueller, 2020). Moreover, a recent study examined the influencers affect on purchase decision of consumers in the context of Facebook in Jordan, revealed that trustworthiness and quality is strongly linked with the purchase decision (AL-Sous, 2023). Another study revealed that the similarity, trustworthiness, and attractiveness affect the trust of the followers and purchase intentions (Lou,

2019). Additionally, a study shows that contemporary celebrities (influencers) such as YouTubers, bloggers are more influential than traditional celebrities. This is due to their characteristics like credibility and relatability (Djafarova, 2017). Influencers are proficient to develop close relationships with their followers which ultimately develops trustworthy and reliable links with their followers (Belanche et al., 2020). Thus, by considering the strong connection between influencer characteristics and purchase intentions in recent literature (Gomes et al., 2022; Foroughi et al., 2024), we hypothesize that H1: Influencer marketing is positively associated with followers' purchase intentions in social commerce.

Perceived Value:

Value is created when consumers believe that the benefits they receive outweigh the sacrifices they make (Zeithaml, 1988). This perception is shaped by various marketing activities and plays an important role in consumer satisfaction. When consumers are satisfied, this satisfaction leads to loyalty, retention, positive word of mouth, a competitive advantage, and increased market share (Morar, 2013). Marketing places value at its core, and perceived value is one of the most important factors in improving customer satisfaction. Researchers often examine perceived value through both single- and multi-dimensional lenses. The single dimensional approach often focuses on economic and utilitarian factors, such as functional performance and price, where value is rationalized primarily on the product's functional utility (Oppong et al., 2021). This approach focuses on balance between price and performance of the product. In contrast, the multi-dimensional perspective consists of the experiential factors that consider the symbolic and subjective elements related to the product and its services (Holbrook, 1982). This perspective focuses on hedonic value related with the experiences, such as pleasure, enjoyment, and emotional satisfaction associated with the use of product and service. For instance, the hedonic value in social commerce refers to intrinsic motivations such as pleasure, playfulness, and fun that consumers experience during online shopping activities (Sharma, 2020).

This perspective emphasizes the hedonic value derived from experiences, such as pleasure, enjoyment, and

emotional satisfaction, linked to the consumption of products or services. For instance, the hedonic value associated with social commerce includes intrinsic motivations like pleasure, playfulness, and fun, which consumers experience during activities like online shopping (Sharma, 2020).

Perceived value concept is originally rooted in economics and psychology domain, making it a critical construct for understanding consumer behavior. It is defined by Zeithaml (1998) as "the overall assessment of the utility of a product based on perceptions of what is received and what is given." Similarly, another researcher defines it as "the net gain the customer receives from the social website". The concept of perceived value has gained significant attention from professionals and researchers since its conception and gained peak attention during 2006 and 2008 specifically within the marketing domain (Ajina, 2019). However, despite its widespread usage, the concept has faced definitional debates and is considered overused or misused (Sánchez-Fernández & Iniesta-Bonillo, 2007). The perceived value is a context specific perception that influences user attitude and behaviors (Lee et al., 2014). The perceived value concept can be used to explore the effect of influencer on their followers due to its effect on the cognition of individual users. Perceived value can affect the decision of the individual follower who follows the influencer. In our research, we are focusing on the relationship between perceived value and behavior of the followers. Considering the importance of perceived value in shaping consumer attitude and behavior, we hypothesize that H2: Influencer marketing is positively related to the followers' perceived value in social commerce.

Research suggests that customer trust and perceived value help in establishing a long-term relationship between customers and brands, which in turn enhances the purchase intention (Hadge, 2023). A study indicated that customers' intention to purchase is strongly influenced by the perceived value of online shopping experiences. The higher the perceived value, the greater the likelihood that customers will make a purchase (Ponte et al., 2015). This positive relationship between perceived value and purchase intention has been observed in across various online shopping contexts, including

social commerce (Gan & Wang, 2017). Building on these findings, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H3: Follower perceive value is positively associated with their purchase intention in social commerce

Trust:

Customers need to trust brand in order to purchase product from the brand. They expect reliability and truth in order to avoid risk associated with the online transaction (Zhao et al., 2020). Trust significantly affects consumers' purchase intentions in online environments, especially among younger generations (Sung et al., 2023). Similarly, several other studies revealed that trust is linked positively with the purchase intentions in digital environment (Chen et al., 2018; Mosunmola, 2019). Another research revealed that trust, perceived usefulness, and attitude are significantly related with purchase intention (Sintia et al., 2023). Trust can reduce consumer's intention to buy from brands in case they sense threat in transaction (Xu & Wang, 2018). As many people exploited social commerce to get short term benefits and many others have reported numerous complaints about trust and privacy issues (Han et al., 2018). Recent research examined the determinants of trust and purchase intention in the social commerce on Instagram. They opted for two types of trust: trust in seller and trust in products and revealed perceived price plays a crucial role and moderates the relationship. If the prices are fair, trust effectively drives purchase intentions. This means that tailored trust-building strategies are essential in social commerce to enhance the trust and convert them into sales (Gunaratne Senali et al., 2024). Therefore, trust become a source of concern as it can decrease or enhances the purchase intention in SC. Thus, our next hypothesis is

H4: Follower's trust has a direct influence on purchase intention in social commerce.

Few studies suggests that customer who perceive higher value of product are more likely trust them. This relationship between perceived value and trust is further supported by another research which

identified a positive direct link between utilitarian and hedonic value of product and trust (Mosunmola et al., 2019). Additionally, another study revealed that customers who perceive greater value in a clothing brand purchase them and trust the brand or retailer more (Karaboğa et al., 2017). Similarly several studies shows a direct relationship between value and building trust in e-tailers (Prameka et al., 2017; Al Huwaishel et al., 2018). Thus, our next hypothesis is H5: Follower's perceive value is positively associated with the trust in influencer in social commerce.

While influencer marketing has been shown to directly shape followers' buying decisions, this effect often works through deeper psychological pathways. One important mechanism is perceived value – how much a follower believes the product or endorsement is worth in terms of usefulness, enjoyment, or emotional benefit. Influencers play a key role in creating this value by offering personalized, relatable, and often aspirational content that resonates with their followers' preferences.

But perceived value alone isn't always enough to convince someone to make a purchase. In the digital world – especially in social commerce – trust is a critical layer. If followers believe that an influencer is honest, knowledgeable, and genuinely recommends products that are valuable, they are more likely to trust both the influencer and the product.

Therefore, influencer marketing does more than just create awareness or desire – it builds a bridge. First, it enhances perceived value; then, this value strengthens trust; and finally, trust motivates the actual intention to buy.

In this way, perceived value and trust act like stepping stones – a chain of influence – that explains how and why influencer marketing leads to purchase intentions. This layered process has been largely underexplored in previous research, particularly in the context of beauty products and social commerce platforms like Instagram.

Hence, we propose the following hypothesis:

H6: The relationship between influencer marketing and purchase intention is serially mediated by perceived value and trust.

Research Model:

The following conceptual framework is developed from the above discussion and hypothesis:

Figure 1: Research Model

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study investigates the relationship between influencer marketing and purchase intentions, focusing on how influencers impact consumer decisions in the beauty sector within emerging economies. We used quantitative data gathering approach to validate our research.

Data Collection:

This section describes the population, sampling process, survey design and statistical method used to test the above mentioned hypothesis.

Sample Selection:

The population for this study includes Instagram users who actively follow beauty influencers. Non-probability sampling was used due to the broad and undefined nature of this population, where the exact number of potential respondents cannot be accurately determined (Latan et al., 2020). Moreover, purposive sampling was used to ensure that respondents were

part of target population ;individuals who engage with beauty influencers on Instagram.Data were collected from 302 followers of beauty influencer via Instagram.

The online form was distributed to collect data.

The demographic data is presented in the table below:

In terms of **gender**, our sample consists of 302 respondents, 39.4% are male, while 60.6% are female. Our sample had a higher representation of female respondents. The age distbution shows that the majority of participants are between the ages of 20 and 29, 53.6 % followed by 30-39 age group with 24.8% of the sample, while 11.9% are under 20. A smaller proportion of respondents are in the 40-49 age group (6.3%) and those aged 50 or older represent only 3.3% of the sample. The education data shows that the majority of respondents held a bachelor's degree, comprising 64.2% of the sample.

Demographics	Number	Percentage
Gender		
Male	119	39.4
Female	183	60.6
AGE		

<20	36	11.9
20-29	162	53.6
30-39	75	24.8
40-49	19	6.3
>50	10	3.3
Education		
Matric	33	10.9
HSSC	36	11.9
Graduation	194	64.2
Masters	29	9.6
PhD	10	3.3

Survey Items:

An online survey instrument was developed, consisting of a series of questions designed to gather relevant data. All items were adapted from previously validated scales in the literature. The survey included two parts: Part 1 captured demographic information such as age, gender, and education, while Part 2 measured the key constructs influencing purchase intention within the context of social commerce in Pakistan. Details of the measurement items are provided in the Appendix."

All constructs demonstrated good to excellent internal consistency, as indicated by their Composite Reliability and Cronbach’s Alpha values. Influencer Marketing (IM) and Perceived Value (PV) showed particularly strong reliability scores. Additionally, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all constructs exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.50, confirming good convergent validity. These results indicate that each construct reliably captures the variance explained by its corresponding items.

Results:

Our model significantly predicts purchase intentions $F(3,298) = 703.02, p < .001$ through regression analysis with $R^2 = .876$. The 87.6 percent value suggest that the variance of purchase intentions can be explained via independent variables in our proposed model. This highlights the strong predictive power of influencer marketing and perceived value in this context.

The results further indicated that the influencer marketing has a significant and positively impact on purchase intentions ($B = .211, t = 4.040, p = 0.000$) and supported our H1. Similarly, our results revealed that perceived value (PV) positively and significantly affect the purchase intention (PI) ($B = .411, t = 7.765, p = 0.000$) and supported H3. Moreover, our study showed that trust significantly and positively affect the purchase intentions ($B = .315, t = 5.913, p = 0.000$). These findings underscore the importance of perceived value and influencer marketing in driving purchase intentions.

Regression Analysis of purchase Intentions:

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficient (B)	t-value	p-value	Hypothesis	Result
Influencer Marketing (IM)	0.211	4.040	<.001	H1	Supported
Perceived Value (PV)	0.411	7.765	<.001	H3	Supported
Trust (TR)	0.315	5.913	<.001	H4	Supported

The study assessed the serial mediation effect of perceived value and trust. The results revealed a significant indirect effect of influencer marketing on purchase intentions through perceived value and trust ($B = .144, t = 5.470$) and supporting the hypothesis

H2. Furthermore, the direct effect of Influencer Marketing on purchase intention was also significant ($\beta = .211, p = 0.001$), This indicates a partial serial mediation effect of perceived value and trust on

purchase intentions. Mediation summary is presented in table below

The study assessed the serial mediation effect of perceived value and trust. The result revealed the significant indirect effect of IM on purchase intentions through (B=.144, t= 5.470) and supporting the hypothesis H5. Furthermore, the direct effect of

Influencer Marketing on purchase intention was also significant (($\beta = .211$, $p = 0.001$), Thus there is a partial serial mediation of perceived value and trust on purchase intentions. Mediation summary is presented in table below

Total effect (Influencer Marketing →Purchase intention)	Direct Effect (Influencer Marketing→Purchase intention)	Relationship	Indirect Effect	Lower bound	Upper bound	t-Statistic	
.8410(.000)	.211(.000)	H4:IM->PV->Trust->PI	.144	.099	.206	5.47	Partial Mediation

The influencer marketing, perceived value and trust are important factors in determining the purchase intention of the followers in social commerce. Our hypothesis were supported in the study. Our results confirm that influencer marketing is a key factor in shaping purchase intentions consistent with the previous research (Yen C. H & Teng, H. Y., 2015; Chi et al., 2011). Perceived value through influencer marketing is a crucial factor in shaping the purchase intentions, as supported by previous studies in the social media context (Ajina, 2019; Chen, & Lin, 2019). Furthermore, influencer marketing is an effective way to establish trust and loyalty among followers (Kim , 2021). However, the perceived commercial nature of influencer posts can diminish this trust (Martínez-López et al., 2020). Thus, this suggest that brands must carefully manage the influencer endorsement to maintain follower’s trust and perceived value to increase purchase intentions. our research also proves that influencer marketing build trust via perceived value. Several studies have investigated the relationship between perceived value and trust in various circumstances and discovered that both perceived value and trust had a large impact on online purchasing intention, with perceived product sacrifice, skill, and compassion being especially relevant determinants (Zhang et al., 2021). Perceived value drives consumer happiness, which in turn influences trust and repurchase intention in e-commerce (Blut et al., 2023). Finally, (Gwin, 2009) emphasised the role of trust and brand relationship quality in increasing perceived value and brand loyalty in the consumer products market. These studies

highlight the important function of perceived value in building trust and we get the similar result in our study. Perceived value that was created through influencer marketing develop follower’s trust and establish purchase intentions in SC. Our study shows that influencer not only enhances perceived value but also builds trust among followers, which drives purchase intentions. These findings suggest that to maximized the purchase drive ,brands should focus on fostering trust and perceived value through carefully cultivated influencer marketing. By doing so, brands can more efficiently convert influencer marketing to increase purchase intentions.

Managerial Implications:

In reality, our data demonstrate a range of variables causing followers to purchase through social media through engaging activities. The findings can help practitioners and online business owners to better understand customer behavior on social media. This study also highlights the impact of perceived value on trust beliefs and purchase intentions. Communicating strong influencer marketing in enhancing the perceived value of things sold online might enhance follower interest in purchasing. Influencers should use limited-time offers or exclusive deals to create a sense of urgency. It will help to drive immediate action from followers. Additionally, online businesses should regard followers' expectations and perceptions of value. Brand managers need to understand that the authenticity and quality of their products are important in social commerce. Businesses can leverage influencer marketing to enhance their

perceived value with followers. Influencer marketing can build long-term relationships with followers through relationship marketing. When selecting an influencer for a brand strategy, E-tailors should be aware of their capacity to effectively communicate value to followers. Organizations should integrate influencer marketing into business strategy, objectives, and finances. Businesses should understand how customers use social media and how they differ in their buying intentions. To maintain long-term growth in the business, marketers should focus on daily social interactions with followers. By omitting this interaction, brand managers put themselves at the vulnerability of losing customers to competition.

Limitations and Future Recommendations:

This study focused on beauty brands shopping in social commerce in the Pakistani market dynamics. The findings of our study provide valuable insights with some limitations that suggest future avenues for upcoming studies. First, the results of our study may not be generalizable, as consumer behavior significantly varies across cultures and geographical contexts. Therefore, we suggest investigation of our model in other countries to validate and extend the applicability of this model. Moreover, this study evaluated influencer marketing, perceived value and trust as independent variables, other studies can test other potential influences on purchase intentions. A few suggestions are customer engagement rate and E-word of mouth can play a crucial role in purchase intentions. Future research should incorporate these factors to develop a more comprehensive understanding of followers' purchase intentions in social commerce. Furthermore, this study measured the purchase intentions rather than actual purchasing behaviour. Future research should aim to bridge this gap by examining how the intentions of followers translate into real purchase action. This could be done through longitudinal studies that track the follower's intentions into actual purchase. Finally, this study focused on beauty products, future research can explore by investigating different product categories. It will provide richer insights into how different product categories enhance social commerce through influencer marketing.

Conclusion

Further research on social commerce is essential to deepen our understanding of consumer behaviour in interactive online environments like Facebook, Instagram etc. Our study offers a model to understand follower purchasing intentions in s-commerce in Pakistan, but its findings should be tested and extended to other countries.

The study found that influencer marketing affects the perceived value of followers who are inclined to buy beauty products through social networking sites. By enhancing trust and perceived value, brands can build stronger customer relationships and increase purchasing intentions. Perceived value not only increases propensity to purchase but also builds confidence in social commerce.

To fully cultivate the potential of social commerce, businesses need to understand the complexity of consumer purchase behavior and adapt strategies accordingly.

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